

Evaluation of the Pterygium Size on the Corneal Astigmatism Pre and Post Excision

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Abstract

Background and Aim: Pterygium is a disorder in which the subconjunctival tissues proliferate as vascularized granulation tissue to invade the cornea, damaging the bowman's membrane and the superficial layers of the stroma. The conjunctival epithelium covers the entire area. This study's objective is to use keratometric readings from an automated keratorefractometry to assess how pterygium-induced astigmatism changes after pterygium removal.

Material and Methods: The study comprised 104 patients who had been given a pterygium diagnosis in total. Before enrolment, a written agreement was obtained from each patient who met the eligibility requirements after being informed about the study. An automated keratorefractometer was used to obtain keratometric results. Calculating corneal astigmatism was done using the difference between K1 and K2.

Results: According to the current study, the mean preoperative K1 value in the study group was 42.260.26 and decreased to 41.550.23 on the first postoperative day (P 0.001). A follow-up after one month revealed a statistically significant (P 0.001) decline in the mean K1 value to 40.310.23. According to the current study, the study group's mean preoperative K2 value was 39.271.01 and increased to 40.070.52 on the first postoperative day.

Conclusion: Pterygium has a significant impact on corneal refractive state, which has been assessed by refraction, keratometry, and corneal topography in numerous investigations. For the evaluation of corneal astigmatism brought on by pterygium, the total area and percentage of the pterygium's expansion onto the cornea are crucial criteria. Early detection and treatment of pterygium reduces its deleterious impact on visual acuity.

Keywords: Astigmatism, Coronal, Pterygium, keratometry

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Introduction

Pterygium is a disorder in which the subconjunctival tissues proliferate as vascularized granulation tissue to invade the cornea, damaging the bowman's membrane and the superficial layers of the stroma. The conjunctival epithelium covers the entire area [1].

In tropical regions, it is highly prevalent. Pterygium development is aided by outdoor labour in environments with high light reflection, such as sand and water. In equatorial regions, its prevalence can reach 22%, while in latitudes above 40 degrees, it is fewer than 2%. The age groups with the

lowest prevalence (0–19 years old) and the highest prevalence (over 60 years old) are in the zones with the lowest and highest UV intensities, respectively [2].

Pterygium patients may experience redness, itching, ocular motility abnormality, and hazy vision. Other than an aesthetic abnormality, some people might not have any symptoms at all [3]. Astigmatism brought on by pterygia is assumed to be the cause of the patients' decreased vision. Astigmatism is the primary cause of pterygium in most cases [4]. This astigmatism develops as a result of a mechanical force that locally flattens the cornea's horizontal meridian up to the leading apex of the pterygium. Pterygium also causes oblique astigmatism, which goes against the general rule [5].

There is little information about the total area and percentage extension of the pterygium onto the cornea and how it affects corneal astigmatism, despite the fact that numerous studies have examined and documented the impact of various sizes of pterygium and of pterygium surgery on corneal refractive status, including astigmatism, keratometry, and corneal topography [6]. This study's objective is to use keratometric readings from an automated keratorefractometry to assess how pterygium-induced astigmatism changes after pterygium removal.

Material and Methods

The current study is an interventional prospective research. The medical college and affiliated hospital's Department of Ophthalmology is where the current study was carried out. The study comprised all primary pterygium patients who presented to the department of ophthalmology. The investigation was conducted over the course of a full year. The Ethical Committee gave its approval to the study before it began.

The study comprised 104 patients who had been given a pterygium diagnosis in total.

Before enrollment, a written agreement was obtained from each patient who met the eligibility requirements after being informed about the study. The following were the admission and exclusion criteria:

Inclusion Criteria: Patients with pterygium and pterygium encroachment more than 2 millimeters on the cornea as well as 1D astigmatism (as determined by automated keratometry).

Exclusion criteria: Patients with ocular trauma, ocular surgery, severe dry eye, recurrent pterygium, double pterygium, pseudo pterygium, acutely inflammatory pterygium, and the presence of any corneal abnormalities including scarring.

Patients were questioned about their concerns after providing written, informed consent, and a thorough clinical examination was performed with reference to the presenting illness. These results were documented on a pre-made proforma.

The best corrected visual acuity was measured during the ocular examination using the Snellen chart. For the purpose of diagnosing pterygium, a thorough anterior segment examination was performed under slit lamp biomicroscopy in diffuse and oblique illumination. By projecting a horizontal slit beam from the limbus to the apex of the pterygium and measuring the length in millimeters, the size of the pterygium was determined using a slit lamp bio-microscope. A tiny, slit laser beam was used to measure the width of the pterygium at its base at the limbus (in millimeters). A small slit beam of light was used to assess the horizontal corneal diameter as well (in millimeters).

The total area was determined by multiplying the pterygium's width (in millimeters) by its horizontal length (in millimeters).

An automated keratorefractometer was used to obtain keratometric results. Calculating

corneal astigmatism was done using the difference between K1 and K2. To rule out severe dry eye, the individuals underwent the Schirmer test 2 and Tear Break up Time. To rule out other corneal disease, fluorescein staining of the cornea was also performed on the study participants.

The data was compiled on a proforma and on Microsoft excel spreadsheet. The statistical analysis was performed. The comparison was done between the baseline to postoperative day one and one month. Pearson correlation coefficient was used to find the relationship between the area of pterygium with pre-operative astigmatism, percentage extension of pterygium with pre-operative astigmatism. A probability value (p value) of < 0.05 was considered as statistically significant.

Results

The Department of Ophthalmology at the hospital and medical college treated 104 patients with primary pterygium in the current prospective interventional trial. The 104 patients in the current study ranged in age from 20 to 65, with a mean age of 28.25 years. The male to female ratio was determined to be 1:1 in the current investigation, which demonstrated equal gender distribution. When the right and left eyes were compared, it was shown that more patients had pterygium in the right eye than the left.

In this study, the mean pterygium size was 4.10 5.24 mm, the mean pterygium breadth was 3.0 9.0 7.21 0.24 mm, and the mean corneal diameter was 11.0 13.0 12.14 0.60 mm. The pterygium size ranged from 2.0 mm to 7.0 mm. According to the present study the mean preoperative K1 value in the study group was 42.26 ± 0.26 which showed a reduction in postoperative day one with a mean value of 41.55 ± 0.23 ($P < 0.001$). One month follow up showed a statistically significant ($P < 0.001$) reduction of mean K1 value to 40.31 ± 0.23 .

According to the present study, the mean preoperative K2 value in the study group was 39.27 ± 1.01 which showed an increase in postoperative day one with a mean value of 40.07 ± 0.52 ($P < 0.001$). One month follow up showed a statistically significant ($P < 0.001$) increase of mean K2 value to 41.60 ± 0.65 .

In this study, the study group's average preoperative astigmatism was 2.660.49. On the first postoperative day, the average astigmatism was 1.360.4 ($P 0.001$). Mean astigmatism decreased statistically significantly to 0.710.78 ($P 0.001$) during a one-month follow-up.

In the current investigation, a significant relationship between the preoperative corneal astigmatism caused by the pterygium and the percentage of pterygium extension onto the cornea was found. In this investigation, it was discovered that postoperative astigmatism reduction rises along with the size of the pterygium.

The average preoperative astigmatism in the first group, where the area of the pterygium is smaller than 8 mm², was 1.30 0.27 and decreased to 0.63 0.26 on the first postoperative day. ($P < 0.001$). In one month, follow up mean astigmatism showed a statistically significant reduction to 0.32 ± 0.17 ($P < 0.001$). In the second group where area of pterygium is considered between than 8 to 12mm² mean preoperative astigmatism was 2.47 ± 0.47 which reduced to 1.10 ± 0.27 on postoperative day one ($P < 0.001$). In one month, follow up mean astigmatism showed a statistically significant reduction to 0.43 ± 0.20 ($P < 0.001$). In the third group, where area of pterygium is considered greater than 12mm² mean preoperative astigmatism was 3.10 ± 0.02 which reduced to 2.07 ± 0.12 on postoperative day one ($P < 0.001$).

In one month, follow up mean astigmatism showed a statistically significant reduction to 2.10 ± 1.26 ($P < 0.001$).

Table 1: Comparison of preoperative and postoperative K1 value

Variable	Mean $\pm$ SD	P value
Preoperative	42.26 $\pm$ 0.26	
Postoperative Day 1	41.55 $\pm$ 0.23	< 0.002
Post operative 1 month	40.31 $\pm$ 0.23	< 0.002

Table 2: Comparison of preoperative and postoperative K2 value

Variable	Mean $\pm$ SD	P value
Preoperative	39.27 $\pm$ 1.01	
Postoperative Day 1	40.07 $\pm$ 0.52	< 0.002
Post operative 1 month	41.60 $\pm$ 0.65	< 0.001

Table 3: Comparison of astigmatism preoperatively and postoperatively

Variable	Mean $\pm$ SD	P value
Preoperative	1.30 $\pm$ 0.27	
Postoperative Day 1	0.63 $\pm$ 0.26	< 0.001
Post operative 1 month	0.32 $\pm$ 0.17	< 0.001

Discussion

The Indian subcontinent has an endemic form of the disease pterygium [1]. Due to astigmatism brought on by pterygium, it is possible for pterygium to reduce visual acuity. The induced astigmatism has been explained by a number of methods. Astigmatism is the primary cause of pterygium in most cases [7]. A substantial pterygium causes the corneal curvature in its horizontal meridian to flatten, leading to up to 1.5 D of with-the-rule astigmatism. Pterygium also causes oblique astigmatism, which goes against the general rule [8].

Pterygium is a clinical condition characterised by a triangular invasion of the bulbar conjunctiva onto the cornea. It takes one of two shapes. In a genuine pterygium, the conjunctiva actively invades the cornea during a degenerative and hyperplastic phase. An inflammatory process leads to a pseudo pterygium [9]. Pterygium does not cause symptoms when it is minor, with the exception of a little irritation during the times of inflammatory engorgement.

Both substantial corneal deformation and the development of significant corneal

astigmatism can result from the advancement of a pterygium onto the cornea. Due to indirect encroachment on the visual axis or directly produced corneal astigmatism (most commonly with the rule), pterygium creates visual issues. A pooling of the tear film, mechanical pressure on the cornea, and the size of the pterygium, particularly the double headed pterygium, are the causes of astigmatism. Refraction, corneal topography, and keratometry have all been used to measure this [10,11].

The induced astigmatism has been explained by a number of methods. These include (a) the tear film collecting at the pterygium's leading edge (2) and (b) the pterygium's mechanical tension on the cornea [11]. Refraction, three corneal topographies, and keratometry have all been used to measure this anomaly. There are several options for treating pterygia. These include topical chemotherapeutic drugs such as intraoperative or postoperative conjunctival or amniotic membrane transplants, external beta irradiation, simple excision, and excision with these grafts. Mitomycin-C [12].

The rise in the 31–40 age range may be due to the fact that patients in this group are more aesthetically concerned and hence seek out ophthalmologists more frequently. The other reason might be because these groups had more aggressive pterygium, greater symptoms, and more frequent hospital visits [13].

A prospective, non-randomized investigation was carried out in 2014 by Prakriti Chourasia *et al* [14] on 50 eyes of 46 patients who had primary pterygium in one or both eyes. Preoperative and postoperative keratometric values were evaluated. After 1, 3, and 6 months following surgery, the mean preoperative refractive astigmatism of 1.02 was reduced to 0.19, 0.14, and 0.11 respectively. In comparison to oblique and vertical meridian, horizontal meridian had the highest preoperative mean astigmatism. According to this study, pterygium removal significantly reduces corneal astigmatism.

When the pterygium area and corneal astigmatism were correlated, it was discovered that as the pterygium area increased, so did the degree of corneal astigmatism. In order to study the effects of pterygium on corneal spherical power and astigmatism, Atsuo Tomidokoro *et al.* [15] performed a prospective, non-randomized, comparative study on 136 eyes undergoing primary pterygium excision. They found that the presence and removal of pterygium significantly affect corneal refraction, including spherical power, astigmatism, asymmetry, and irregularity

According to the findings, there is a statistically significant link between corneal astigmatism and the amount and size of pterygium that extends over the cornea. The preoperative corneal astigmatism increases as the pterygium's region grows. As the pterygium's surface area grows, so does the amount of postoperative astigmatism that is reduced. Preoperative corneal astigmatism

increases together with the percentage expansion of pterygium onto cornea. As the amount of pterygium that extends onto the cornea increases, there is a greater reduction in postoperative astigmatism.

Conclusion

Pterygium has a significant impact on corneal refractive state, which has been assessed by refraction, keratometry, and corneal topography in numerous investigations. For the evaluation of corneal astigmatism brought on by pterygium, the total area and percentage of the pterygium's expansion onto the cornea are crucial criteria. Early detection and treatment of pterygium reduces its deleterious impact on visual acuity.

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